

Thermal Studies on Iron(II) Complexes with Polypyridine and Dicarboxylic Acid Ligands

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The mixed ligand complexes of iron(II) which exhibit spin equilibrium have been synthesized by the reaction of ferrous sulfate with polypyridine ligand (phen/bpy) and sodium oxalate. The thermograms indicate that the dehydration of the complexes is followed by the elimination of the oxalate and then polypyridine ligand. The DSC of both the complexes exhibit two endotherms corresponding to the dehydration and final decomposition step. The stability of phen complex is more than that of the bpy system.

The study of transition metal complexes exhibiting spin transition phenomenon is significant since various factors like nature of the ligand, crystallinity, solvent employed for crystallization etc. affect their magnetic behaviour¹. Recently, we have reported the influence of solvent on the spin equilibrium of iron(II) complexes. The thermal studies on these systems provide complementary data to the nature of the species at elevated temperature and also explain the relative thermal stability of the various systems.

The present study aims at the analysis of the thermal behavior of the mixed ligand complexes of iron(II) obtained from a polypyridine ligand (bpy/phen) and an aliphatic dicarboxylic acid(ox), which are found to exhibit spin equilibrium. The TG and DSC studies of these systems are discussed.

Results and Discussion

The thermograms of the complexes reveal that the dehydration of water in the crystal lattice commences in both the cases below 80°. However, in the case of phen system, the lattice water is only partially removed at the first inflexion point and it continues in the second step, where the decomposition of oxalate ligand begins. Now the complete elimination of both water and oxalate takes place and the process is complete at 210°. Finally, the phen ligand is removed from the system. The earlier reports² on the thermal decomposition of $\text{FeC}_2\text{O}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in nitrogen atmosphere indicate the formation of different types of products, like Fe_2O_3 , Fe_3O_4 and metallic iron. The resulting composition of the final product obtained in the present investigation corresponds to 20 and 21%, indicating the formation of metallic iron and a mixture of FeO and metallic iron in the case of bpy and phen system respectively. It has also been reported³, that in reducing as well as in inert atmosphere the glycolates of certain metal ions like Fe^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Ni^{2+} etc. result in the formation of either their oxide or mixture of oxides and the metal. The decomposition product in those cases were found to be $\text{FeO}/(\text{Cu} + \text{Cu}_2\text{O} + \text{CuO})/(\text{Ni} + \text{NiO})$ according to the metal ion used in the system. Thus the formation of the metallic oxide as well as the metal during the thermal degradation of the complexes

with divalent metal ion in inert atmosphere is in conformity with the observations made earlier. The IR spectrum of the product from bpy system also shows weak bands at 400–650 cm^{-1} indicating the presence of FeO in the final product.

The dehydration step in the bpy system commences near 46° and as in the case of phen complex this step is coupled with the decomposition of the oxalate ligand and they are complete at 162°. The removal of bpy ligand from the decomposed fragment is the last step and the residue left behind is a mixture of metallic iron and FeO. The weight-loss and the corresponding transitions are further corroborated by the fact that the derivatograms exhibit peaks coinciding with the inflexions observed in the thermograms. It is interesting to note that all the three steps occur at a lower temperature in the case of bpy complex when compared to those of phen complex. The enhanced thermal stability is attributed to the presence of additional aromatic ring and consequent higher electron density at the reactive centre.

Broadbent *et al.*⁴ also demonstrated that it is possible to decide whether an oxalate will decompose to the metal or its oxide at a particular temperature in inert atmosphere based on thermodynamic considerations. This is obtained from the relative values of free energies of formation of metal oxides to that of the formation of CO_2 by the oxidation of CO at the temperature of decomposition. In the present case, the decomposition of the oxalate ligand is followed by the removal of polypyridine ligand, which also influences the course of the decomposition. The enhanced stability attributed to the phen system results in the formation of metallic iron as the final product of degradation, while the presence of FeO and metallic iron in the other case indicates only a partial effect on the decomposition of oxalate.

If water molecule is bonded to the metal ion then dehydration will be followed by the decomposition of the oxalate ligand. This is clearly reflected in the present case wherein the removal of water is not complete in one stage and it is accompanied by the decomposition of the oxalate ligand. This crystal structure studies made in the case of

picolyamine complexes of iron(II)⁵ establish the fact that there is H-bonding between the lattice water and the central metal ion, which results in the increase of solvent-cation contact and a subsequent reduction in the cation-ligand contact. Also the combined weight-loss due to the elimination of water, oxalate and polypyridine is slightly less than the theoretically calculated value indicating that oxygen has been taken up by the metal ion in the formation of metal oxide in the final product.

The DSC of both the complexes exhibit only endotherms, and in the case of the bpy system a sharp endotherm is observed at 86.6° while two well-defined endotherms, at 106.6 and 397° are observed in the case of the phen complex. However, an ill-defined endotherm is seen at 380° in the former case. The first endotherm corresponds to the dehydration step, while the second one is due to the decomposition of the complex, which is finally obtained as a stable residue. Thus the trend observed in the TG of the complexes is also followed in the DSC of these complexes. The earlier report on the thermal behavior of ferrous oxalate in both air and in nitrogen atmosphere exhibits one exotherm (280°) and two endotherms (200 and 365°) respectively, whereas ferric oxalate shows two exotherms and two endotherms. The formation of the final product in a metal oxalate depends on the cleavage of M-O bond or C-O bond as the case may be.

The present study clearly shows the thermal degradation pattern of both the iron complexes in which the decomposition is preceded by dehydration. The final residue in the case of the phen complex is metallic iron, and in the bpy system a mixture of metallic iron and FeO were obtained. The temperature at which the weight-loss commences in all the three stages in the thermograms and temperature at which the endotherm appears suggest a higher thermal stability for the phen system as compared to the bpy complex.

Experimental

The iron(II) complexes, viz. [Fe(phen)₂ox].5.2H₂O and [Fe(bpy)₁ox].0.3H₂O were synthesized according to the reported procedure⁶. The complexes were not crystallized from any other organic solvent and only polycrystalline samples were employed for the earlier as well as the present study.

A Dupont-2000 thermal analyzer having a 2950 TG module and DSC module was used for thermal characterization of the complexes. About 30 mg of sample was used in each experiment. The heating rate was maintained at 10°/min and the sample was heated upto 650° in oxygen-free nitrogen atmosphere.

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